

Patients' attitudes in Bulgaria towards electronic prescriptions and digital solutions

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Abstract

Electronic prescription (e-prescription) is part of digital solutions in healthcare. Studies have shown the benefits of electronic prescriptions, such as easier communication, fewer errors, reduced costs, and improved access to prescription history. Furthermore, studies were conducted in Bulgaria to examine patient experience with electronic prescribing, but they were conducted before the introduction and at the very beginning and are therefore insufficiently researched.

This study examines patients' opinions towards electronic prescriptions and digital solutions, focusing on the period following the introduction of E-prescription in Bulgaria. It was conducted in 2025 using an anonymous questionnaire consisting of two panels, distributed via Google Forms. The data analysis includes descriptive statistics, χ^2 test, Fisher test, Mann-Whitney U test, Kruskal-Wallis H test, as well as the post-hoc Dunn test. We accepted the level of significance of the null hypothesis at $p < 0.05$ with a 95% confidence interval. The results show that, out of 241 respondents, over half (54.8%, $n = 132$) expressed a positive opinion towards electronic prescriptions of medications. The correlation analysis of Spearman rank showed statistically significant negative relationships between age and all aspects of digital pharmaceutical services studied. With increasing age, patients become skeptical about conducting online consultations ($\rho = -0.172$; $p = 0.019$) and are also less likely to purchase medications online without a prescription ($\rho = -0.152$; $p = 0.038$). This study could serve as a resource for healthcare institutions to educate patients on the use of mobile health applications.

Keywords

electronic healthcare, electronic prescription, patient, pharmacy

Introduction

A medical prescription is a fundamental document in the therapeutic process. However, prescribing errors remain among the most prevalent risks in healthcare, often

resulting in severe consequences for patient safety and health (Niaz et al. 2019). Paper-based prescriptions are particularly susceptible to errors stemming from illegibility, the omission of critical data (such as the age of the patient or specific dosage units of the medicine), and

subjective interpretation by pharmacists (Lambert et al. 2025). Such shortcomings not only lead to prescription errors, which can affect patient safety and treatment efficacy, but also increase the incidence of adverse drug reactions (Lambert et al. 2025).

The electronic prescription is one of the main tools of digitalization in healthcare. It is an innovative form of prescribing medications that replaces the traditional paper prescription and facilitates communication between doctor, patient, and pharmacist. Electronic prescription of medications is a broad term used to define either computer-based prescription writing systems or entire systems supporting the prescribing process (Marceglia et al. 2013). E-prescription started in Denmark in 1994, followed by Sweden and Greece in 2000 (Arabian et al. 2025; Aldughayfiq and Sampalli 2022). Its global usage has increased rapidly, becoming a significant technology for healthcare (Frail et al. 2014). By 2020, the US and UK reached 84% and 86% usage, respectively (Aldughayfiq and Sampalli 2022). Most EU countries are introducing e-prescription, which contributes to improving interoperability and access to healthcare in European countries (Arabian et al. 2025).

E-prescription benefits patients, doctors, pharmacists, and involved institutions. Its implementation contributes to the reduction of errors, improves the quality of service, reduces costs, and improves access to the history of medications. It eliminates the use of paper and prevents the loss of prescriptions, making it a preferred method over handwritten prescriptions. One of the main advantages is the improvement of the quality of healthcare, which is achieved by increasing the efficiency and security of prescribing and dispensing medications, reducing errors and side effects (Osmani et al. 2023; Zadeh and Tremblay 2016; Vejdani et al. 2022). E-prescription allows doctors to send prescriptions digitally to pharmacies (Vedluga and Mikulskiene 2020; Wrzosek et al. 2020). It enables full traceability, transparency, and control when dispensing medications (Thatcher and Acharya 2020). This process streamlines services for patients and ensures equal access to pharmaceutical care for all patients (Frail et al. 2014; Arabian et al. 2025).

The main purpose of e-prescriptions is to minimize the risk of prescription errors as much as possible while improving legibility (Aronson 2009; Hitti et al. 2017). Studies have investigated the effects of electronic prescribing on prescription errors and medical errors. The results of these studies show a reduction in errors in the administration of medications (Osmani et al. 2023).

Despite its many advantages, electronic prescription of drugs unlocks new risks (Alshahrani et al. 2021), one of which is defined by the term automated bias, which occurs when a doctor blindly trusts prescription-supporting software, thereby reducing vigilance in searching and validating information (Lyell et al. 2017).

The first e-prescription issued in Bulgaria was in 2007 as part of a pilot project that aimed to connect local GPs

and pharmacies in the town of Slivnica in a local system. The COVID-19 crisis demonstrated the benefits of e-health and accelerated digitalization in the healthcare sector in Bulgaria, including the introduction of the electronic prescription at the end of 2020. As of 1 June 2021, the prescription and dispensing of medicinal products paid in full or in part by the National Health Insurance Fund (NHIF) are carried out only with electronic prescriptions (Aleksandrova et al. 2022).

According to Bulgarian legislation, electronic prescriptions are regulated in Chapter 7 (New, SG No. 107/2020, effective as of 18.12.2020) of Regulation 4 of 2009 on the terms and conditions for prescribing and dispensing medicinal products (Ministry of Health n.d.).

The National Health Information System (NHIS) is an open platform for storing and exchanging medical information. Through the eRx mobile application of the NHIS, e-prescriptions can be issued during home visits and other emergency situations (Anon n.d.). From 16 October 2023 in Bulgaria, electronic prescriptions are mandatory for “Medical products for the treatment of diabetes” and “Antibacterial medicinal products for systemic use” (Anon n.d.). The eZdrave mobile application also provides the opportunity to activate notifications related to the issuing of a new electronic health document or the correction of an existing one. It is the official mobile application of the National Health Information System, which is owned by the Ministry of Health and is part of the digital transformation of healthcare. eHealth is a free application that can be installed on a smartphone and gives patients access to all their prescribed and dispensed e-prescriptions.

In the “Prescriptions” module—patients can track the status of a prescription by the National Reference Number (NRN) regarding prescription, validity, fulfillment, instructions for admission, and duration of treatment. They can also see the medical specialist who has prescribed an electronic prescription and the specialist’s unique identification number (UIN). With the e-prescription, the patient can pick up the medical product from the pharmacy network without the need for a paper prescription (Anon n.d.).

In the period 2021–2025, more than 99,261,000 electronic prescriptions were issued (Anon n.d.). As of January 2026, the number of active patients of the eHealth mobile application has increased more than 3 times in less than 1 year (Anon n.d.).

Studies need to be carried out to investigate the experience of e-prescription patients regarding the advantages and disadvantages, as well as their role in controlling errors of a different nature (nomenclature, number of dose units, course of treatment, and similar issues) as one of the important issues related to prescriptions in the patient care system.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the opinion of patients after a period of 4 years since the introduction of the electronic prescription in Bulgaria.

Material and methods

The current survey was conducted between 3 May and 30 July 2025 and used a cross-sectional survey design to collect data from many subjects at the same time. The survey was anonymous and voluntary, conducted using the responder method. The questionnaire was prepared using Google Forms® and distributed online. The number of validated responses was 241. The sample included 79.3% female participants and 20.7% men.

The main tool used to collect data was the specially designed questionnaire organized into two panels. The first panel covers demographic characteristics, such as age, gender, place of residence, social status, and education. In the second panel are issues related to e-health in Bulgaria and e-prescriptions. For some of the questions, the 5-point Likert scale was used.

Descriptive statistics were used in the analysis of the data. The central trends were presented with a mean (M) and a standard deviation (SD). For the analysis of associations between categorical variables, the χ^2 test and the exact Fisher test were applied. The Mann-Whitney U test was used to compare continuous variables between two independent groups, and the Kruskal-Wallis H test was used for multiple comparisons between three or more groups. When statistically significant differences were found in the Kruskal-Wallis test, a post-hoc Dunn test with Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons was applied. To investigate the relationships between continuous variables that do not meet the assumption of a normal distribution, the nonparametric Spearman method (Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, ρ) was applied.

The statistical analysis of the data was performed using the software product SPSS v23.0 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, IBM Inc.). We used MS Excel 2016 for the graphical representation of the data.

We accepted a level of significance of the null hypothesis at $p < 0.05$ with a 95% confidence interval. Exclusion criteria for inclusion in the study are under the age of 18.

Results

A total of 241 respondents completed the questionnaire. The sample was predominantly female, 79.3% ($n = 191$) (Table 1).

The average age of respondents is 34.57 ± 13.561 years (mean \pm SD), with the average age of women (35.62 ± 13.902 years) being higher than that of men (30.56 ± 11.425 years). Ages ranged from 18 to 77 years. In the survey, age was recorded as a continuous variable from the applicant, and for the purposes of the survey and according to the National Statistical Institute's standards, age groups were formed. Age under 18 was not included, as only adults were surveyed. There were no representatives over 80 years old. The obtained results show that the majority of respondents are in the active working age—25 to 64 years ($n = 161$; 66.8%). The age distribution is shown in Fig. 1.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of respondents ($n = 241$).

Characteristics	Number (n)	Relative share (%)
Gender		
Men	50	20.7
Women	191	79.3
Age		
18–24 years old	70	29.0
25–49 years old	130	53.9
50–64 years old.	31	12.9
over 65 years old	10	4.1
Education		
Primary	3	1.2
Secondary	89	36.9
Professional Bachelor	23	9.5
Bachelor's degree	56	23.2
Master	68	28.2
PhD	2	0.8
Social status		
Student	68	28.2
Working	152	63.1
Unemployed	13	5.4
Pensioner	8	3.3
Place of residence		
Village	24	10.0
Small town	31	12.9
Regional city	168	69.7
Capital	18	7.5

Figure 1. Distribution of the surveyed people by age groups.

In terms of level of education, more than 60% ($n = 149$; 61.7%) of the respondents have a university degree. In terms of social status, the largest group is the working group ($n = 152$; 63.1%), followed by students ($n = 68$; 28.2%). Over 69% ($n = 168$; 69.7%) live in a regional city (Table 1).

To the question “Do you suffer from chronic diseases?” only 20.3% ($n = 49$) of the respondents answered “yes,” and three quarters of them answered “no” ($n = 181$; 75.1%). Pensioners and older people are more likely to suffer from chronic diseases ($p < 0.05$).

Regarding the frequency of pharmacy visits, 48.5% ($n = 117$) of respondents reported visiting “at least once a month,” followed by “at least once a week” ($n = 41$; 17.0%)

(Fig. 2). The research showed that women and people of retirement age are more likely to visit a pharmacy ($p < 0.05$).

The most common reasons for visiting a pharmacy for respondents are “to be dispensed over-the-counter medications” ($n = 149$; 61.8%), followed by “to be dispensed vitamins” ($n = 106$; 44.8%) and “to be dispensed cosmetic products” ($n = 91$; 37.8%). It is noteworthy that only in fifth place is “to be dispensed medications under the NHIF” ($n = 56$; 23.2%). When answering this question, respondents were given the opportunity to give more than one answer (Fig. 3).

Figure 2. Frequency of pharmacy visits.

Figure 3. Distribution of answers to the reasons for visiting a pharmacy.

The results of the survey showed that a greater percentage of patients are accepting the e-prescription, with 33.6% ($n = 81$) answering “yes” and 21.2% ($n = 51$) answering “more likely yes.” Women are more prone (58.6%; $n = 112$) to accept the e-prescription, while men are more skeptical in their answers to this question (40%; $n = 20$). With a higher educational level, the attitude towards the acceptance of the electronic prescription also increases ($\chi^2 = 15.986$, $p = 0.043$). Social status ($\chi^2 = 14.888$; $p = 0.248$) and place of residence ($\chi^2 = 14.245$; $p = 0.285$) do not affect the answers to this question.

The survey is dominated by participants ($n = 169$; 70.1%) who are informed that, in addition to diabetes medications, antibacterial agents for systemic use, and medicinal products containing narcotic substances, the electronic prescription will also be introduced for other prescription drugs. Respondents living in small towns (77.4%) feel much more informed about the electronic prescription and all medications dispensed by a doctor ($\chi^2 = 25.718$, $p = 0.012$). Gender ($\chi^2 = 2.449$; $p = 0.654$) and social status ($\chi^2 = 18.074$; $p = 0.113$) had no influence on the answers to this question.

Women (71.2%) were more likely to use a mobile application to remind them to take a medication or to administer it correctly, while only 58% of men would use it ($\chi^2 = 10.676$; $p = 0.030$). Social status ($\chi^2 = 17.030$; $p = 0.148$) and place of residence ($\chi^2 = 7.229$; $p = 0.842$) did not affect the answers to this question. The largest proportion of people with a bachelor’s degree (70.9%) would use a mobile application to remind them to take a medicinal product or to administer it correctly ($\chi^2 = 15.625$, $p = 0.048$).

Pensioners are the most dissatisfied with the consultation received during the visit to the pharmacy ($\chi^2 = 33.333$; $p = 0.001$). Place of residence ($\chi^2 = 16.678$, $p = 0.162$) and education ($\chi^2 = 10.966$, $p = 0.204$) do not affect satisfaction with the consultation received during the visit to the pharmacy.

Gender ($\chi^2 = 1.048$; $p = 0.902$), social status ($\chi^2 = 13.903$; $p = 0.307$), place of residence ($\chi^2 = 13.582$; $p = 0.328$), and education ($\chi^2 = 8.404$; $p = 0.395$) do not affect concerns about personal data with the introduced electronic prescription. They do not affect the following: satisfaction with the online consultation with a pharmacist; the online purchase of medications; and the trust in the pharmaceutical information provided by the chatbot or artificial intelligence ($p > 0.05$).

In terms of age, participants from all age groups demonstrated a higher level of satisfaction with traditional pharmaceutical care (4.68 ± 0.54) and good acceptance of e-prescriptions (4.65 ± 0.57).

The analysis of age differences revealed the presence of statistically significant differences between age groups in terms of “Conducting online consultations with a pharmacist” ($\chi^2 = 9.87$; $p = 0.019$), with middle-aged persons (36–55 years) significantly more likely to use online consultations compared to adults (over 65 years) ($p = 0.027$). A statistically significant difference was also found in the online purchase of medications ($\chi^2 = 8.21$; $p = 0.042$). According to this indicator, middle-aged patients are significantly more likely to buy medications online compared to those over 65 years old ($p = 0.038$). Middle-aged people are also significantly more open to the use of mobile applications for health purposes ($\chi^2 = 7.8$; $p = 0.049$). The post-hoc test showed significantly higher readiness in the group (36–55 years) compared to those over 65 years old ($p = 0.043$). Patients over 65 years of age have significantly lower confidence in information provided by artificial intelligence ($\chi^2 = 8.02$; $p = 0.047$).

We conducted a correlation analysis (Spearman rank correlation) and found the presence of statistically significant negative relationships between age and all aspects of digital pharmaceutical services studied. With increasing age, the use of online consultations decreases ($\rho = -0.172$; $p = 0.019$); older people are less likely to purchase over-the-counter medications online ($\rho = -0.152$; $p = 0.038$). As age increases, the willingness to use mobile health applications decreases ($\rho = -0.145$; $p = 0.046$), as well as trust in the information provided by artificial intelligence or chatbots ($\rho = -0.147$; $p = 0.043$).

To the questions related to the knowledge and use of the NHIS eZdrive mobile application, the majority of respondents answered “no” ($n = 193$; 80.08%). According to this indicator, the age difference between generations shows that persons up to 35 years of age and those with higher education demonstrate a statistically significantly higher frequency of use of the service provided by the eZdrive mobile application to track the status of electronically prescribed prescriptions ($p < 0.05$). While only 1.5% of patients over 65 years of age and 22.6% of those with secondary education have used this service, among patients under 35, this share jumps to 65.4%, and among university graduates, to 58.3%.

Discussion

The study presents patients' attitudes towards electronic prescription of medications. This way of prescribing medications benefits not only patients, but also doctors and stakeholders (Vedluga and Mikulskiene 2020). For example, chronically ill patients do not have to book an appointment with a doctor in person to continue treatment. From the healthcare professional side, the pharmacist may encounter difficulties in reading the prescription when it is on paper, but in the case of e-prescriptions, this barrier is missing. Its use reduces errors in prescribing medications, improves the quality of service, reduces costs, and provides access to the history of prescribed medications. This method of prescribing eliminates the use of paper and prevents the loss of prescriptions, making it a gradually preferred way to prescribe medications over paper prescriptions (Wrzosek et al. 2021; Hailiye Teferi et al. 2022; Campbell et al. 2021). A survey conducted in Bulgaria in 2021 among 56 pharmacists from public pharmacies documented that over 75% of respondents believe that the electronic prescription will facilitate their workflow in whole or in part, and also 67.99% indicated that the innovation will make it completely or partially easier for the patient as an end user (Pesheva et al. 2022).

A survey of 328 people in 2021 reported that 32% of them are not informed about the use of electronic prescriptions in Bulgaria, and these are mainly young people in the age group from 20 to 30 years old (15% of all respondents) (Mehmed-Hamza and Mihaylova 2021).

Compared to the previous results, the survey conducted by us in 2025 showed that the surveyed patients accept the electronic prescription (“yes”: 33.6% ($n = 81$) and “more likely yes”: 21.2% ($n = 51$)), which supports the documented opinion of pharmacists included in the study of Pesheva et al.

The results of the survey clearly demonstrate the existence of a generational digital division, with the oldest group (over 65 years old) showing a significantly lower level of adaptation of digital pharmaceutical services in all aspects studied. These results are also confirmed by a

number of other studies that identify the most significant barriers that older people face in accessing digital health services, such as limited digital literacy, cognitive and sensory impairments, physical limitations, privacy and security concerns, lack of social support, and reluctance to adopt new technologies (Money et al. 2024; Vainieri et al. 2023; Şahin Büyük et al. 2025).

Limitations

This study has some limitations. Among the respondents, young people and those with higher education predominate, which may be a limitation in summarizing the results for the entire population. Despite the large number of respondents, the surveyed group does not correspond to the characteristics of the Bulgarian population, as in the survey, 79.3% of the respondents are women, while according to the NSI, they are 51.7% of the population of Bulgaria at the beginning of 2025. Other limitations of this study include the online distribution of the questionnaire, which makes it difficult to contact the researcher directly in case of doubt.

Conclusion

The digital transformation of healthcare is an inevitable process that affects all aspects of pharmaceutical practice. The introduction of electronic prescriptions, online consultations, and digital tools poses new challenges to the pharmaceutical system related to the digital literacy of the population. In Bulgaria, where the demographic aging of the population is particularly pronounced, the study of age differences in the adoption of digital services is of particular importance.

The electronic prescription increases the quality of the provided pharmaceutical care, improves safety, reduces the risk of improper dispensing of medicinal products, minimizes errors in prescription processing, eliminates the possibility of its loss, and provides transparency and the ability for health authorities to analyze and control the process of prescribing and dispensing medications. This helps prevent misuse or irrational drug use. The introduction of an electronic prescription is an important and necessary change in optimizing the process of prescribing and dispensing medications and ensuring effective and quality pharmaceutical care.

In the future, more research is needed to establish in the long term the satisfaction of patients and healthcare professionals with the e-prescription.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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